

Modern Friedel-Crafts chemistry. Part-26[†]. A facile synthesis of *trans*-2-methyl-1-phenylindan via rearranged intramolecular cyclialkylation of 1,2-diphenyl-2-methyl-2-propanol under Friedel-Crafts conditions

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1,2-Diphenyl-2-methyl-2-propanol (1) was prepared by two alternative Grignard methods. Treatment of 1 with AlCl₃, AlCl₃/CH₃NO₂ or K10 clay catalyst in benzene, toluene or dichloromethane solvent at varying temperatures for varying times gave *trans*-2-methyl-1-phenylindan (4) as sole or major product. Side products including isomeric alkenes 7 and 8, isomeric chlorides 9 and 10, isomeric triarylated isobutanes 11-14, 1-methyl-3-phenylindan (5) and 2-methyl-1-phenylindene (6) were also detected by GC-MS technique. Mechanistic interpretations and explanatory comments are offered.

In previous papers of this series, we reported the detection of 2-methyl-1-phenylindan (4, Scheme 1) as a significant component amongst the products of Friedel-Crafts

alkylations of benzene with both 1,2-dibromo-3-chloro-2-methylpropane¹ and 3-chloro-2-(chloromethyl)-1-propene². To rationalise this, we proposed a series of

Scheme 1

[†]For Part-25 : see Ref. 1.

Table 1. Conditions and results of Friedel-Crafts reactions of 1,2-diphenyl-2-methyl-2-propanol (**1**)

Sl. no.	Reactants and conditions						Product composition, compd. no. (%) ^{a,b}
	1 (mol)	ArH (mol)	CH ₂ Cl ₂ (ml)	Catalyst (mol or g)	Time (h)	Temp. (°C)	
1.	0.01	PhH (0.1)	5.0	AlCl ₃ (0.011)	0.5	25	<i>Trans-4</i> (77.2), <i>cis-4</i> (2.3), 5 (6.2), 6 (2.8), unident. (11.5)
2.	0.01	PhH (0.1)	5.0	AlCl ₃ (0.011)	1.5	25	<i>Trans-4</i> (90.0), <i>cis-4</i> (3.0), 6 (2.0), unident. (5.0)
3.	0.01	PhH (0.1)	None	AlCl ₃ (0.011)	1.0	60	<i>Trans-4</i> (34.0), <i>cis-4</i> (3.0), (<i>Z</i>)- 8 (8.0), (<i>E</i>)- 8 (16.0), 9 (19.0), 10 (2.0), 11 (7.5), unident. (10.5)
4.	0.01	PhH (0.1)	None	AlCl ₃ (0.011)/CH ₃ NO ₂ (0.033)	2.0	25	<i>Trans-4</i> (21.5), <i>cis-4</i> (1.5), (<i>Z</i>)- 8 (12.6), (<i>E</i>)- 8 (20.1), 9 (32.6), 10 (5.0), unident. (6.7)
5.	0.01	None	5.0	AlCl ₃ (0.011)	0.5	25	<i>Trans-4</i> (77.0), <i>cis-4</i> (3.0), (<i>Z</i>)- 8 (Tr), (<i>E</i>)- 8 (Tr), 9 (11.0), unident. (9.0)
6.	0.01	PhH (0.1)	None	AlCl ₃ (0.011)/CH ₃ NO ₂ (0.033)	1.0	60	<i>Trans-4</i> (64.4), <i>cis-4</i> (11.0), (<i>Z</i>)- 8 (Tr), (<i>E</i>)- 8 (2.4), 9 (2.0), 10 , (Tr), 13 , (2.0), unident. (18.2)
7.	0.01	None	8.0	AlCl ₃ (0.011)	1.5	25	<i>Trans-4</i> (85.0), <i>cis-4</i> (3.0), 9 (7.0), unident. (5.0)
8.	0.01	PhH (0.1)	None	K10 Clay (1 g)	20.0	Reflux	<i>Trans-4</i> (69.0), <i>cis-4</i> (5.5), (<i>Z</i>)- 8 (Tr), (<i>E</i>)- 8 (Tr), unident. (25.5)
9. ^c	0.01	PhCH ₃ (0.1)	None	K10 Clay (1 g)	24.0	Reflux	<i>Trans-4</i> (50.0), <i>cis-4</i> (5.0), 12 and 14 isomers (1.6 + 2.0 + 2.5 + 11.7 + 8.8), unident. (18.4)
10.	0.01	None	8.8	K10 Clay (1 g)	24.0	Reflux	1 (47.0), 7 (10.0), (<i>Z</i>)- 8 (10.0), (<i>E</i>)- 8 (14.0), unident. (19.0)

^aPercentage composition as recorded by GC-MS analyses. The listed products were identified mainly through comparison of GC-MS data with those of reference and/or previously reported samples.

^bMost Friedel-Crafts reactions are complex and the presence of unidentifiable materials is expectable.

^cSee experimental section for more details.

consecutive carbocation transformations leading to the intermediacy of carbocations **2** and/or **3** which can subsequently proceed to form **4** (Scheme 1).

In this paper we wish to support this view through a study of the behaviour of 1,3-diphenyl-2-methyl-2-propanol (**1**), as a nominated precursor for carbocation **2** and hence **3**, under various Friedel-Crafts conditions.

Results and discussion

The desired alcohol **1**, obtained by two alternative Grignard routes, was subjected to a series of ten variable experiments whose conditions and results are depicted in Table 1. Meanwhile, the carbocation transformations believed to be responsible for the formation of the detected products are formulated in Scheme 1.

Referring to Table 1 and Scheme 1, the following significant observations can be pointed out: (i) The production of indan **1** as almost sole or major product in most experiments gives experimental support to earlier assumptions^{1,3}. (ii) The fact that this occurred in spite of the presence of nucleophilic benzene or toluene confirms the reported preference of intramolecular over intermo-

lecular alkylations in similar cases^{4,5}. (iii) The failure of intramolecular ring closure in Exp. 10 is probably due to the considerably lower reflux temperature of CH₂Cl₂ (b.p. 40–41°) relative to other used solvents. That also explains why about 50% of the starting alcohol was recovered unchanged.

In conclusion, it is worthy to point out that apart from theoretical aspects, the results of this work reaffirms the facility by which indan derivatives can be obtained through direct and rearranged cyclialkylations^{4,5}. As the results indicated, 2-methyl-1-phenylindan (**4**) was obtained not only in high yields but also in high stereochemical *trans*-purity, using a variety of conditions.

Experimental

The instruments reported earlier¹ were used and starting chemicals and solvents were pure grade supplied by Aldrich and were used as purchased.

Synthesis of starting material and reference samples:

Synthesis of 1,1-diphenyl-2-methyl-2-propanol (1):

Alcohol **1** was synthesised in 80–85% yields by two

alternative Grignard routes : one involving the reaction of 1,2-diphenyl-2-propanone with methylmagnesium iodide and another involving the reaction of 1-phenyl-2-propanone with benzylmagnesium chloride. Both reactions were conducted following standard procedures but using saturated NH_4Cl solution for decomposition.

Attempted purification of the above alcohol by either distillation or chromatography over silica or alumina resulted in complete or partial elimination. Accordingly, the crude alcohol, which was freed from all solvents and low boilers by elongated rotary evaporation at RT, was used as such in the next step. As apparent from GC-MS data the purity was about 97%. The alcohol, which gave satisfactory elemental analysis, showed the following spectral data : IR ν_{max} (neat) 3544 and 3250 (OH), 3080–2860 (CH), 1600 (aromatic C), 1490, 1450, 1375, 1095, 1030, 950, 890, 755, 725, 700, 530, 507 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz) CDCl_3 : δ 0.95 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.55 (1H, brs, OH, D_2O exchangeable), 2.75 (4H, dd, J 13.2 Hz, two diastereotopic CH_2 groups), 7.2 (10H, slim m with two weak side peaks at 6.7 and 7.66 aromatic protons); MS, m/z (%), 226 (M^+ , very weak), 208 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.5), 193 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $-\text{CH}_3$, 1.9), 135 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, 42), 117 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, $-\text{CH}_3$, 27), 91 (PhCH_2 , 100), 77 (11), 65 (29), 57 (31).

Conversion of 1,1-diphenyl-2-methyl-2-propanol (1) to a mixture of 2-benzyl-1-phenyl-1-propene (7) and (Z) and (E)-1,2-diphenyl-2-methyl-1-propene Z-8 and E-8, respectively : The procedure described earlier for dehydration with NaHSO_4 was essentially followed⁶. The resulting product was subjected to both IR and GC-MS analyses; while IR showed the disappearance of OH bands, GC-MS analysis showed the following composition : 7 (2%), (Z)-8 (19%), (E)-8 (39%) and other side products (4.5 + 32.5 + 4.1%). The mass spectra for the resulting products were as follows :

Alkene 7 : m/z (%), 208 (M^+ , 31), 193 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_3$, 13), 179 (7), 165 (3), 128 (15), 129 (19), 117 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, 100), 116 (18), 115 (58), 105 (9), 92 (14), 91 (PhCH_2 , 47), 77 (5), 65 (25), 51 (12).

Alkene (Z)-8 : m/z (%), 208 (M^+ , 42), 193 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_3$, 29), 179 (14), 178 (16), 165 (5), 152 (3), 130 (17), 129 (13), 115 (C_5H_7 , 100), 91 (PhCH_2 , 35), 77 (7), 65 (15), 51 (11).

Alkene (E)-8 : Mass spectrum was identical with that of (Z)-8.

A major side product that constituted 32.5% of the reaction product gave the following mass data : m/z (%), 210, 20, 195 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_3$, 100), 178 (8), 165 (21), 153

(10), 141 (4), 115 (3), 94 (5), 89 (8), 82 (11) 76 (6), 63 (3). The exact identity of this product has not yet been disclosed.

Conversion of 1,1-diphenyl-2-methyl-2-propanol (1) to the corresponding 2-chloro-1,2-diphenyl-2-methylpropane (9) : This was carried out by treating the alcohol with Lucas' reagent as directed⁷ with the exception that the resulting chloride was taken in ether, washed with 5% sodium carbonate solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was then removed by rotary evaporation. The remaining yellowish liquid product was subjected to both IR and GC-MS analyses : IR showed weak OH bands at 3544 and 3450 cm^{-1} due to some unreacted alcohol. GC-MS showed the product to consist of : 7 (4%), (Z)-8 (3%), (E)-8 (7%), unreacted 6 (17%) and desired chloride 9 (50%). Chloride 9 gave the following MS data : m/z (%), 244/246 (M^+ , 19/6), 208 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{Cl}$, 13), 153/155 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, 31/111), 152/154 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, $-\text{H}$, 24/9), 117 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, $-\text{Cl}$, 42), 116 (33), 105 (12.6), 91 (PhCH_2 , 100), 77 (14), 65 (31), 51 (29).

Alkylation procedures :

The amounts of reactants were those given in Table 1 and the practical steps were essentially similar to those applied in earlier papers⁸.

Mass spectra of reaction products :

The mass spectra of compounds 1, 7, (Z)-8, (E)-8 and 9 were similar to those of the reference samples described above. Meanwhile, the spectra of compounds 4 (*cis* and *trans*)^{1,2} and 13² were similar to those reported in other papers. The MS spectra of the rest of the products were as follows :

1-Methyl-3-phenylindan (5) : m/z (%), 208 (M^+ , 100), 193 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_3$, 67), 179 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, 48), 178 (40), 165 (11), 152 (5), 139 (1), 130 (39), 115 (57), 103 (21), 91 (PhCH_2 , 25), 89 (18), 82 (12), 77 (18), 65 (10), 63 (10), 51 (15). This spectrum is similar to that recorded in the data base for the same compound.

2-Methyl-1-phenylindene (6) : m/z (%), 206 (M^+ , 100), 191 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_3$, 53), 189 (16), 165 (10), 128 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$, 20.0), 115 (8), 101 (14), 91 (PhCH_2 , 15), 76 (8), 51 (6).

Chloride 10 : m/z (%), 244/246 (M^+ , 5/1.5), 208 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{Cl}$, 9), 193 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{Cl}$, $-\text{CH}_3$, 6), 178 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{Cl}$, $-\text{2CH}_3$, 3), 165 (2.6), 130 (3), 125 (3), 119 (29), 118 (6), 117 (13), 116 (3), 115 (14), 104 (4), 92 (24), 91 (PhCH_2 , 100), 77 (4), 65 (11), 51 (6).

2-Methyl-1,2,3-triphenylpropane (11) : m/z (%), 286 (M^+ , 0.5), 195 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{PhCH}_2$, 67), 179 (3), 178 (5), 167 (14), 152 (3), 117 (27), 115 (16), 92 (8.6), 91 (PhCH_2 ,

Note

100), 77 (4), 65 (9), 51 (5).

1,3-Diphenyl-2-methyl-x-tolylpropanes (12 and 14) : In experiment 9, GC-MS data traced the presence of five such isomers showing parent M⁺ peaks at *m/z* 300, base peaks at *m/z* 181 and corresponding to molecular formula C₂₃H₂₄. These were present in percentage compositions of 1.6, 2.0, 2.5, 11.7 and 8.8%, respectively, according to increasing GC retention times. The mass spectra that were highly similar could be presented by the following example : *m/z* (%), 300 (M⁺, 5), 182 (19), 181 (M⁺-C₆H₅CHC₆H₄CH₃, 100), 166 (16), 165 (17), 115 (6), 105 (4), 91 (PhCH₂, 18), 77 (4), 65 (5), 51(3).

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